

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 3

 Acceptance of papers **March, 2026**

Acceptance of papers

Published monthly

Topics

economics, technology, social sciences

Editorial board:

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of
Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Professor,
Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), (Malaysia)

Asongu SImplice
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences (PhD),
USA

Abdikarimova Dinara Rustamxanovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Alimardonov Ilkhom Muzrabshokovich
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Razakova Barno Sayfiyevna
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Khasanov Sarvar Ulugbek ugli
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna
Associate Professor (PhD)

CONTENTS

FINANCING OF SMALL BUSINESSES THROUGH INVESTMENT LOANS BY COMMERCIAL BANKS.....	15
Yangiboyev F.B.	
INTEGRATION OF THE TRANSPORT SECTOR INTO THE GREEN ECONOMY AND IMPACT ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: ECOLOGICAL TRANSFORMATION AND INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS	20
Narziyev Umidjon Bakhriylayevich	
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN INCREASING THE INVESTMENT ACTIVITY OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES	24
Begamov. S.X.	
AN ENHANCED FINANCING MODEL FOR STARTUP PROJECTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF UZBEKISTAN	27
Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna	
STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING INVESTMENT POTENTIAL.....	32
Tillayeva Barno Ramizitdinovna	
THE IMPORTANCE OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HOTEL MANAGEMENT.....	36
Husenova Madina Farkhodovna	
MARKETPLACES AND ECONOMIC SECURITY IN UZBEKISTAN: RISKS AND REGULATION	42
Umarkhodjayeva Zaynabkhon Nodirkhonovna	
TECHNOLOGICAL STRENGTH AND PROPERTIES OF METAL OF AUSTENITIC JOINTS DURING WELDING WITH VARIOUS FLUXES.....	47
Khudoykulov Nurilla Zikirillaevich, Khudoyorov Sardor Sadullaevich	
MODERN SYSTEMS OF PRODUCT COST CALCULATION: METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS AND DIRECTIONS OF PRACTICAL TRANSFORMATION	51
Abdumalik Abdiraximovich Tulyaganov	
SUPPORTING ECONOMIC EXPANSION AND MAXIMIZING PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY WITHIN A MARKET ECONOMY.....	56
Aytmuratov Qutlimurat Jalgasovich	
SUCCESS FACTORS OF DIFFERENTIATION STRATEGY IN A MARKET ECONOMY.....	62
Sodiqov Miraxror Abbos ugli	
THE “MISSING MIDDLE” PROBLEM IN SOCIAL PROTECTION SYSTEMS AND MECHANISMS FOR ADDRESSING IT	67
Farrukh Juraqulovich Bafoev	
IMPROVING POPULATION INVESTMENT ACTIVITY THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF BANK BROKERAGE SERVICES AND FINANCIAL LITERACY IN FORMING A SECURITIES PORTFOLIO IN THE KHOREZM REGION	72
Bakhtiyorov Khudaybergan Hamdam ugli	
DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR AND ITS IMPACT ON POVERTY REDUCTION.....	79
Dauletmuratov Adilbay Mirzabaeovich	
THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF A SYNERGETIC APPROACH IN DEVELOPING THE MANAGEMENT SKILLS OF SCHOOL DIRECTORS.....	84
Yusupova Dilnoza Fayzullayevna	
REGIONAL INNOVATION DEVELOPMENT INDICATORS AND THEIR EVALUATION SYSTEM	89
Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich	
GADGETS AND VALUES: HOW DOES THE VIRTUAL WORLD IMPACT THE EDUCATION OF YOUTH?	97
Makhmudova Sohiba Ravshan kizi, Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli	
WAYS TO IMPROVE SERVICE QUALITY AND SAFETY IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	101
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES BASED ON FOREIGN EXPERIENCE.....	104
Eshbaeva Shahnoza Faxriddinovna	

IMPROVING METHODS FOR DETECTING FRAUD CASES IN CURRENT ASSET AUDITS.....	108
Mavlyanova Dilobar Makhkamovna	
GLOBAL TRENDS IN WORLD MARKETS AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL TRADE	113
Meliqulov Abduhalil Norinovich	
THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF FORMING AND APPLYING THE INTEGRATION MECHANISM OF SMALL BUSINESS	119
Rustambek Ibragimovich Israilov	
THE IMPORTANCE OF USING PERFORMANCE INDICATORS IN IMPROVING ROAD MANAGEMENT METHODS.....	125
Sirojiddin Yadgarov	
WAYS TO IMPROVE BANKING EFFICIENCY IN THE CONDITIONS OF TRANSFORMATION.....	131
Babakhanova Dildora Rustamovna	
THE ROLE OF PROGRAM-BASED BUDGETING MECHANISMS IN ENSURING STATE FINANCIAL SECURITY	137
Abduganiyev Uchkun Khabibulla ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY ON SOCIAL JUSTICE THROUGH PEFA AND CEQ METHODOLOGIES.....	143
Zokirjonov Muhammadsodiq Ravshanbek ugli	
MANAGERIAL MECHANISMS OF CORPORATE HYBRID BUSINESS MODELS: FINTECH INTEGRATION IN E-PAYMENT SYSTEMS OF UZBEKISTAN	151
Mokhirakhon Abdullaeva	
TOKENIZATION OF REAL SECTOR ASSETS AND DEEPENING OF CAPITAL MARKETS: A NEW FINANCIAL ARCHITECTURE FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES	156
Oybek Qo'shboqov	
TECHNOLOGIES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN OPTICAL COMMUNICATION AND THEIR INTEGRATION INTO INTELLIGENT TUTORING SYSTEMS.....	162
Maxamadov Rustam Xabibullayevich, Djamatov Mustafa Xatamovich	
APPROACHES TO ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GOVERNMENT SUPPORT FOR SMALL BUSINESSES IN THE REGION	169
Madraimova Marxamat Raximberganovna	
INNOVATIVE WAYS TO INCREASE THE INVESTMENT CAPACITY OF REGIONS BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES.....	174
Qabilov Anvar Eshpulatovich	
TAXATION OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES AND THE ORGANIZATION OF THEIR ACCOUNTING SYSTEMS.....	179
Abdullayev Abdurauf	
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF THE VEGETABLE FARMING SECTOR IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	183
Sobir Xasanov	
AI FOR TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO UNIVERSITY STUDENTS.....	191
Nurzhanova Zhainash, Rajapova Guldona	
REVIEW OF THERMAL STRENGTHENING METHODS FOR ROLLING ROLLS MADE OF ALLOY STEELS USED IN THE PRODUCTION OF SEAMLESS PIPES	198
Saydumarov Botir Muradovich, Xasanov Kamoliddin Akmal o'g'li, Ergashev Davron Ortiq o'g'li, Saydumarov Botir Muradovich	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCING THE COUNTRY'S INTERNATIONAL IMAGE: IN THE EXAMPLE OF SOUTH KOREA.....	203
Kurolov Maksud Obitovich	
SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF TASHKENT CITY: TRENDS AND KEY INDICATORS.....	212
Karimova Shirin Zokhid qizi	
PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS INFLUENCING PROCRASTINATION AMONG GENERATION Z UNIVERSITY STUDENTS.....	216
Abdukaxxorova Durdona, Qadamova Rayhona, Muhammadova Shaxzoda, Salimov Ozodbek, Hojiyeva Iroda Avezovna	

IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF PRIVATE SCHOOLS BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES.....	222
Shohida Esanova	
ASSESSMENT OF TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY IN CENTRAL ASIAN TELECOMMUNICATION OPERATORS USING THE DEA-CCR MODEL: THE EXPERIENCE OF UZBEKTELEKOM AK	230
Salimova Husniya Rustamovna	
DETERMINANTS OF MUTUAL TRADE BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE CIS COUNTRIES	235
Munisa Turdibaeva	
INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS.....	241
Mekhmonaliev Ulugbek Erkinjon ugli	
PROSPECTS FOR ENSURING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES THROUGH THE USE OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES	248
Abbosbek Jurayev	
COMPLIANCE OF BANKING AI SYSTEMS WITH EU AI ACT REQUIREMENTS AND THEIR ROLE IN RISK MANAGEMENT	253
Usmonov Faridun F., Zainalov Zh.R.	
A MODEL FOR DETECTING URBAN INFRASTRUCTURE PROBLEMS IN CITIZENS' APPEALS BASED ON GEOLOCATION FEATURES	258
Mallayev Oybek Usmankulovich, Gazatov Jamoliddin Abduvoidovich, Aliyev Jaloliddin Kokand oglu	
DETERMINATION OF THE INFORMATIVENESS OF INPUT PRINTS USING THE MULTI-CRITERIA DISPERSION METOD	264
Turapov Ulugbek Urazkulovich, Akulbayev Musabek Islamovich, Dzhanatayeva Sholpan Kalmakhanovna, Madalievna Gul'nar Urazalievna	

DETERMINATION OF THE INFORMATIVENESS OF INPUT PRINTS USING THE MULTI-CRITERIA DISPERSION METHOD

Turapov Ulugbek Urazkulovich

Associate Professor of the Department of "Information Systems and Technologies"
Tashkent State Agrarian University
Republic of Uzbekistan
Email: tuu_1224@gmail.com
ORCID: 0000-0001-7274-4162

Akulbayev Musabek Islamovich

Procurator for Science, Candidate of Sciences, Professor
University of Friendship of Peoples, Academician A. Kautbekova
Republic of Kazakhstan

Dzhantayeva Sholpan Kalmakhanovna

Senior Lecturer of the University of Friendship of Peoples, Academician A. Kautbekova
Republic of Kazakhstan

Madalieva Gul'nar Urazalievna

Senior Lecturer of the University of Friendship of Peoples, Academician A. Kautbekova
Republic of Kazakhstan

Abstract: In this article, the initial data of the selected input parameters were processed using 7 local criteria, and scientific research was conducted on the problem of determining the informativeness of the output parameters as a result of voting and ordering the level of informativeness in relation to the studied object (informativeness by color). In order to increase the level of accuracy, it has been established that the multi-criteria dispersion method can be used in the formation of a set of informative parameters of input data. As a result, it is possible to solve the problem of forming a set of informative parameters and assessing the adequacy of the model. In this case, we used existing local criteria, and each criterion determines the order of informativeness for each of its parameters based on its own conditions. This repetition is carried out according to 7 criteria, the results of each criterion are summarized to form an informativeness matrix. As a result, a new multi-criteria dispersion method was created, which clarifies the high adequacy of constructing a mathematical model.

Key words: informativeness, ranking, mathematical model, local, criterion, object, multi-criteria, dispersion method.

INTRODUCTION

There are many processes and events today that do not have quantitative characteristics to describe them, or they change rapidly. Mathematical models also use the relationships between input and output variables derived from different considerations. In cases where it is not possible to substantiate the results of experiments or tests and to evaluate the results of decisions made, the method of expert evaluation is used to study the nature of the process or event [1]. The complexity of the formation of the research object or the lack of complete information about the nature of the object requires the use of expert systems. The examination process, on the other hand, involves the identification of a hypothesis that is true on the basis of an overall assessment by each expert from among the predicted hypotheses presented (based on selected factors). As a result, the factor or indicators that significantly affect the object are regulated [2].

The purpose of this article is to study the criteria for regulating the input and output parameters of the object under study using the method of experts.

If it is not possible or appropriate to assess the performance of the objects directly, then the coloring method can be used. The coloring process indicates which of the objects being studied is important. The following methods of coloring are widely used in practice [3,4]:

- simple coloring;
- direct staining;
- pairwise comparison, etc.

The simple staining method is based on arranging objects in ascending or descending order according to their characteristic factors, indicators and traits. In painting, the expert assigns a natural number to each object in order, that is, each object is colored based on its properties. The number of colors is equal to the number of sorted objects. If an object is being studied in N , the color of the most influential object by its nature is denoted as 1, and the color of the least influential object is denoted by N . The value of an object's color actually represents its number in an ordered row of colors. For example, if the row of colors is 1,3,5,7,7,10, the color corresponding to 5 numbers is equal to 3.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The problem of determining the informativeness of input features (prints) has been widely studied in statistical analysis, pattern recognition, and decision-making theory. In particular, the concept of informativeness is closely related to the ability of features to discriminate between classes and to reflect the essential properties of the analyzed system. Kolesnikova S.I. emphasizes that different types of features possess varying levels of informativeness, and their evaluation requires the application of statistical and analytical methods that account for variability, stability, and contribution to classification accuracy. The author highlights the importance of dispersion-based approaches in identifying the most informative attributes, especially when dealing with heterogeneous data structures.

A significant contribution to feature selection problems is presented in the work of Zagoruyko N.G., Kutnenko O.A., and Borisova I.A., where the GRAD algorithm is proposed for selecting informative sub-features. This approach focuses on decomposing complex features into smaller components and evaluating their individual informativeness. Such decomposition is particularly relevant for multi-criteria dispersion methods, as it allows a more precise estimation of the contribution of each component to the overall variability and decision-making process.

Grigan A.M. considers management diagnostics as a multi-criteria process in which the selection of informative indicators plays a key role. According to his research, effective diagnostics requires combining quantitative and qualitative indicators, which aligns with the principles of multi-criteria dispersion analysis. This approach ensures a comprehensive evaluation of system performance and supports more reliable managerial decisions.

The methodological foundation of concordance analysis is also essential in assessing informativeness. The concordance coefficient, as described in methodological sources, serves as a statistical tool for measuring the degree of agreement among expert evaluations. Its application enhances the reliability of selected informative features, particularly in cases where subjective judgments are involved.

An important early contribution to the field is provided by Rastrigin L.A., Khamdamov R.H., and Turapov U.U., who developed a multidisciplinary statistical approach to assessing the informativeness of quantitative features. Their work demonstrates that dispersion-based indicators can effectively capture the variability and significance of features across different conditions. This approach forms the basis for modern multi-criteria dispersion methods, which integrate statistical measures to evaluate the relative importance of input prints.

Overall, the reviewed literature indicates that the determination of informativeness is a complex, multi-dimensional problem that requires the integration of statistical dispersion measures, algorithmic feature selection techniques, and expert-based evaluation methods. The multi-criteria dispersion method emerges as a robust analytical tool that combines these approaches, enabling a more accurate and comprehensive assessment of input feature informativeness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on collecting input feature data from experimental observations and existing datasets, followed by preprocessing and normalization. The analysis employs a multi-criteria dispersion method to evaluate the variability and significance of each feature. Statistical measures, including variance and concordance coefficients, are applied to identify the most informative inputs and assess their contribution to overall system performance.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In some cases, as a result of the expert giving the same color to several objects, the number of objects, which are differentiated by the number of colors, remains the same. In such cases, objects are given standardized colors. In this case, the number of standardized colors is assumed to be n . Objects with the same color are assigned an X_S standardized color. The value of a standardized color is equal to the arithmetic mean of the places of objects of the same rank by color. For example, in the table below, five objects (factors) are given the colors x_i ($i = 1, \dots, 5$) according to Table 1 (Table 1).

Table 1. Assign colors to objects

i	1	2	3	4	5
X_i	1	2	3	2	3

The standardized color of the second and fourth objects, which correspond to the second and third places in terms of color, is $X_S = (2 + 3) / 2 = 2,5$. The standardized color of the fourth and fifth objects, corresponding to the fourth and fifth places in terms of color, is $X_S = (4 + 5) / 2 = 4,5$. As a result, the final view of the object is shown in Table 2 below (Table 2).

Table 2. Using standardized colors, reassignment of ranks to objects

i	1	2	3	4	5
x_i	1	2,5	4,5	2,5	4,5

The set of colors obtained by coloring n objects $X_S(n)$ is defined as follows:

$$X_S(n) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$$

where x_i is the rank corresponding to the i -th object. In fact, applying this formula to Table2, we can be sure that $X_S(5) = 5(5+1)/2 = (1+2,5+4,5+2,5+4,5) = 15$

If the staining is performed by an expert in k , then the color of each object x_{ij} ($i = \overline{1, n}; j = \overline{1, k}$) is determined as the final color by the colors determined by all experts. The object with the smallest set of colors is given the highest (first) color, otherwise the lowest n colors are given. The rest of the objects are arranged in the order of growth of the sum of colors relative to the first object.

The main advantage of the method of painting is explained by its easy implementation. The main disadvantages of this method are:

- coloring a small number of small objects, because if their number exceeds 15–20, it is difficult to color them;
- in this way, the question of how important the objects under study differ from each other in importance remains unresolved.

Direct staining method. This method is based on qualitatively describing the degree of significance of the process or factors when it is difficult to quantify them. In this way, the expert uses their own scale to color the objects in the proposed range of colors. When the number of objects is large, it is difficult to use the direct staining method.

Pair comparison method. This method of coloring is convenient when the number of objects is large. Based on this method, objects are compared in pairs to determine which is more important in each pair of objects. To do this, if the number of objects is n , the expert elements x_{ij} form a square matrix of dimension $n \times n$. The elements of the matrix assume the following values:

if the i -th object is more important than the j -th object, $x_{ij} = 1$;

if the j -th object is more important than the i -th object, $x_{ij} = 0$.

Suppose that objects O_1, O_2, O_3, O_4 and O_5 are required to be painted by an expert. In this case, the expert can construct the following matrix (Table 3):

Table 3. Pair comparison matrix

	O ₁	O ₂	O ₃	O ₄	O ₅	Total color
O ₁	0	0	1	1	0	2
O ₂	1	0	1	1	0	3
O ₃	0	0	0	0	1	1
O ₄	0	0	1	0	1	2
O ₅	1	1	0	0	0	2

As you can see from the table, the most important object here is the O₂ object, the most insignificant object is the O₃ object. Taking into account the relative importance of the remaining O₁, O₃ and O₄ objects, the order of the objects can be arranged as follows:

$$O_2, O_5, O_1, O_4, O_3.$$

The results of any expert are not convincing. Indeed, if the conclusions of the experts differ sharply (for example, if half of the experts are the first color for the factor x_i, and the color of the remaining experts is the last color), then the consensus criterion is used. The criterion for evaluating the results of any expert is called the consensus criterion (or indicator). The higher the coherence of the experts, the higher the confidence in the results of the expert evaluation [4].

There is a need to quantify the degree of coherence of experts and to explain the inconsistency of expert opinions [5]. The measure of conformity is determined on the basis of statistics available to all experts. If the conclusions of the experts do not differ much, then the level of agreement of the experts can be considered good.

The purpose of assessing the consistency of an expert's opinion is to identify a group of experts who agree with each other. The high final agreement of all groups of experts can be the only final assessment. It is necessary to separate a subgroup of experts with a high degree of consensus from a group of experts with a low level of consensus, and to analyze the work of the group's experts in order to determine the reasons for differences in the views of this subgroup. If the reason for the difference of opinion of the experts is the dishonesty of some of them, then it is necessary to reorganize the expert assessment.

Each expert has his own personal assessment, but the agreement factor can be used to verify the final result of the group of experts. The concordance coefficient is used to assess the coherence of the opinions of experts. This coefficient was introduced by Maurice George Kendall, a well-known statistician in the United Kingdom [4].

Suppose that m requires an expert to evaluate n an object. In this case, the coloring matrix is measured in m*n || r_{ij} || (j=1,..., m; i = 1,..., n). Here r_{ij} is the rank assigned to the i-th object by the j-th expert. The values of the elements of the matrix are equal to one of the natural numbers 1,..., n set by the experts, indicating the importance of the objects.

$$r_i = \sum_{j=1}^m r_{ij}, \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$$

The total color of the object's significance can be defined as the sum of the colors on each column of the matrix:

$$r_1 < r_2 < \dots < r_{n-1} < r_n.$$

The color of this collection shows the importance of the objects in the assessment of all experts. The result is a sequence of n objects arranged as follows:

Given that r_i quantities are random quantities, we determine their variance estimates. According to the requirement of the minimum standard error, the variance estimate can be determined as follows:

$$D = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (r_i - \bar{r})^2, \tag{1}$$

where $\bar{r} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n r_i$ is determined by the formula and represents the mathematical expectation.

The coefficient of coherence is an immeasurable quantity and is defined as the variance relative to the maximum variance as follows:

$$W = \frac{D}{D_{max}}. \tag{2}$$

determined by the maximum value of the variance estimate, depending on the number of objects and experts, is determined by the following equation:

$$D_{max} = \frac{m^2(n^3 - n)}{12(n-1)} = \frac{m^2(n^2 + 1)}{12}. \quad (3)$$

Using the notation $S = \sum_{i=1}^n (r_i - \bar{r})^2$, Equation (1) can be expressed as follows:

$$D = \frac{S}{n-1}. \quad (4)$$

Considering equations (3) and (4), the coefficient of agreement is expressed as follows:

$$W = \frac{12 S}{m^2(n^3 - n)} \quad (5)$$

Equivalent objects are usually given the same colors, and such colors are called linked colors. The values of the linked colors are equal to the arithmetic mean of the colors. If there are bound colors in the staining, then the maximum value of the variance decreases and the coefficient of concordance is determined by the following relationship:

$$W = \frac{12 S}{m^2(n^3 - n) - m \sum_{j=1}^m T_j}. \quad (6)$$

In formula (6), the color index associated with the j -th rank is denoted by T_j . In turn, the value of this indicator is found in the following formula:

$$T_j = \sum_{k=1}^{H_j} (h_k^3 - h_k).$$

Here $H_j - j$ is the number of groups with the same color as the color, and $h_k - j$ is the number of colors with the same color in the k group.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it should be noted that the agreement coefficient takes values between 0 and 1. The fact that the value of the agreement coefficient is close to 0 means that the agreement is low. If the value of the coefficient is less than 0.3, it means that the opinions of the experts do not agree with each other, that is, there is no consensus. Also, the values of the coefficient of agreement between 0.3 and 0.7 and greater than 0.7 correspond to the average and high agreement, respectively. In the case of $W = 1$, the experts agree.

When arranging the parameters by the method of expert evaluation, all input and output parameters are determined. These input and output parameters must be sufficiently studied. Otherwise, their use in the model will not be effective.

List of used literature:

1. Kolesnikova S.I., Methods of analysis of informativeness of various types of symptoms // Vestn. Tomsk State University: Management, computer technology and computer science. 2009. № 1 (6). C. 69–80.
2. Zagoruyko N.G., Kutnenko O.A., Borisova I.A., Selection of informational sub-signs of signs (Algorithm GRAD) // Mathematical methods of image recognition: docl. 12 th Vseros. conf. M., 2005. p. 06-109.
3. Grigan A.M., Management diagnostics: theory and practice: Monograph / A.M. Grigan. Rostov n / D: Izd-vo RSEI, 2009. 316 p.
4. <https://autogear.ru/article/349/619/koeffitsient-konkordatsii-primer-rascheta-i-formula-chto-takoe-koeffitsient-konkordatsii/>
5. Rastrigin L.A., Khamdamov R.H., Turapov U.U., Multidisciplinary statistical assessment of informative quantitative symptoms. On Sat. "Automation of production". TashGTU. Tashkent, 1991, p.113-115.

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 3

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles
Published every
monthly

Directions
Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

 Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

**ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO
THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633**

CONTACT:

 Contact us
+998 50 737 87 88

 Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

 Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>